

Survey 3 – General population

The survey, conducted among 2,000 households as part of a pricing experiment, is detailed in the following paper: *Hofmann, Matthias, and Turid Siebenbrunner. 'A Rich Dataset of Hourly Residential Electricity Consumption Data and Survey Answers from the iFlex Dynamic Pricing Experiment'. Data in Brief 50, No. 109571 (1 October 2023).*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109571>.

The survey data are published at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/8248802>

This document is published at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/11580541>

Question Q1: Sex

Question Q12: Age

Question Q15: Are you responsible for paying the electricity bill?

Question Q16: How many people, yourself included, usually lived in your household in the period January - March 2021?

Question Q17_1: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 0-1 years

Question Q17_2: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 2-5 years

Question Q17_3: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 6-15 years

Question Q17_4: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 16-22 years

Question Q17_5: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 23-29 years

Question Q17_6: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 30-49 years

Question Q17_7: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 50-66 years

Question Q17_8: In what age group (s) are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are... 67 years and older

Question Q1: What type of building do you live in? Is it a...

Question Q2: How large is the home in square meters?

Question Q3: Do you own the home?

(IF Question Q3 = Yes)

Question Q4: Do you have a rental unit in the home?

(IF Question Q4 = Yes)

Question Q5: Does the rental unit has a separate electricity meter?

Question Q6_1: How is the home heated? Electric heaters (panel heaters, freestanding heaters, oil-filled radiators)

Question Q6_2: How is the home heated? Electric underfloor heating (heating cables, heating foil)

Question Q6_3: How is the home heated? Air-to-air or air-to-water heat pump

Question Q6_4: How is the home heated? Geothermal / rock heat

Question Q6_5: How is the home heated? Fireplace or wood stove

Question Q6_6: How is the home heated? Oil / paraffin / gas / bio oven

Question Q6_7: How is the home heated? District heating or other shared solution for heating in the building

Question Q6_8: How is the home heated? Waterborne heat that is heated with electricity in your own home

Question Q6_9: How is the home heated? Other type, enter:

Question Q6_10: How is the home heated? Don't know

Question Q7: How is the hot water heated in your home?

Question Q8: Do you have an electric car(s) in the household that is occasionally charged at home?

(IF Question Q8 = Yes)

Question Q9: How is the electric car(s) usually charged?

(IF Question Q9 = At home on the same electricity meter as the rest of the home)
 Question Q10: Do you control the charging of the electric car(s) to avoid hours of high electricity prices?

Question Q11: What type of electricity contract do you have?

Question Q12: What is the highest completed education in the household?

Question Q13: What is the total gross income before taxes of the household?

Question Q14: On how many weekdays (Monday-Friday) was at least one person at home during the day (9 am - 4 pm) during an average working week in the period January - March 2021?

Question Q15: Do you agree or disagree with the following statements? People who adjust their electricity consumption based on the price of electricity should be able to save on electricity costs.

Question Q16: Do you usually follow actively your own electricity consumption?

(IF Question Q16 = Yes)

Question Q17_1: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? Electricity bill

(IF Question Q16 = Yes)

Question Q17_2: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? Directly from the electricity meter

(IF Question Q16 = Yes)

Question Q17_3: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? Website (electricity supplier, grid company, Elhub, etc.)

(IF Question Q16 = Yes)

Question Q17_4: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? App (electricity supplier, grid company, etc.)

(IF Question Q16 = Yes)

Question Q17_5: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? Email or SMS

(IF Question Q16 = Yes)

Question Q17_6: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? Other:

Question Q18: Do you follow actively how electricity prices vary from day to day and hour to hour?

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_1: How do you get information about electricity prices? Electricity bill

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_2: How do you get information about electricity prices? Media / news

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_3: How do you get information about electricity prices? Website (electricity supplier, grid company, Nordpool, etc.)

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_4: How do you get information about electricity prices? App (electricity supplier, grid company, Nordpool, etc.)

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_5: How do you get information about electricity prices? Email or SMS

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_6: How do you get information about electricity prices? From work

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_7: How do you get information about electricity prices? Other:

(IF Question Q18 = Yes)

Question Q19_8: How do you get information about electricity prices? Don't know

Question Q20_1: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home?
Lower electricity bill

Question Q20_2: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home?
Electricity-saving measures that are easy to do manually

Question Q20_3: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home?
Electricity-saving measures that happen automatically so that I don't have to think about it

Question Q20_4: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home?
Electricity-saving measures that do not affect the comfort at home

Question Q20_5: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home?
Test new technology to control electricity consumption

Question Q20_6: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home?
Less negative impact on nature and climate from electricity production and electricity grid

Question Q20_7: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home?
Reduce the need for electricity grid development

Question Q20_8: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home? If many others do

Question Q20_9: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Other:

Question Q20_11: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home? None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption

Question Q20_12: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption in hours of high electricity prices, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Don't know

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
 Question Q21_1: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Have almost no ability to reduce electricity consumption

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
 Question Q21_2: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Do not know how I can reduce electricity consumption

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
 Question Q21_3: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Reduction in comfort and other negative consequences are too large

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
 Question Q21_4: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Do not want to spend time on this

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
 Question Q21_5: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? My electricity costs are not that high

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
 Question Q21_6: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Do not want to change my electricity consumption no matter how much I can save

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
Question Q21_7: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Other:

(IF Question Q20_11 = None, does not want or can not reduce electricity consumption)
Question Q21_8: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Don't know

(IF Question Q20_11 = No answer)
Question Q22: Would you use a free information service that notifies you when the price of electricity the next day would be very high for a few hours?

(IF Question Q22 = Yes)

Question Q23: How much higher did the expected cost of electricity for the entire next day have to be for you to want to be notified? ... Kroner higher compared to a normal winter day.

(IF Question Q22 = No)

Question Q24_1: Why do you not want to use such an information service? Get the information already through other channels

(IF Question Q22 = No)

Question Q24_2: Why do you not want to use such an information service? Do not want to spend time on this

(IF Question Q22 = No)

Question Q24_3: Why do you not want to use such an information service? My electricity costs are not that high

(IF Question Q22 = No)

Question Q24_4: Why do you not want to use such an information service? Other:

(IF Question Q22 = No)

Question Q24_5: Why do you not want to use such an information service?

(IF Question Q20_11 = No answer, for all following questions)

Question Q25_a: Imagine that there is a high electricity price some weekdays (Monday - Friday) in winter. How much money do you have to save on the electricity bill to reduce electricity consumption a few hours in the middle of the day with a high electricity price... A few hours 1 weekday 1 winter month when the electricity price is high

Question Q25_b: Imagine that there is a high electricity price some weekdays (Monday - Friday) in winter. How much money do you have to save on the electricity bill to reduce electricity consumption a few hours in the middle of the day with a high electricity price... A few hours 5 weekdays 1 winter month when the electricity price is high

Question Q25_c: Imagine that there is a high electricity price some weekdays (Monday - Friday) in winter. How much money do you have to save on the electricity bill to reduce electricity consumption a few hours in the middle of the day with a high electricity price... A few hours all weekdays 1 winter month when the electricity price is high

Question Q26_a: Imagine that there is a high electricity price for 2, 4, or 8 consecutive hours one weekday (Monday - Friday) in winter. How much money do you have to save on the electricity bill to reduce electricity consumption during these hours in the middle of the day with a high electricity price... 2 consecutive hours 1 weekday 1 winter month when the electricity price is high

Question Q26_b: Imagine that there is a high electricity price for 2, 4, or 8 consecutive hours one weekday (Monday - Friday) in winter. How much money do you have to save on the electricity bill to reduce electricity consumption during these hours in the middle of the day with a high electricity price... 4 consecutive hours 1 weekday 1 winter month when the electricity price is high

Question Q26_c: Imagine that there is a high electricity price for 2, 4, or 8 consecutive hours one weekday (Monday - Friday) in winter. How much money do you have to save on the electricity bill to reduce electricity consumption during these hours in the middle of the day with a high electricity price... 8 consecutive hours 1 weekday 1 winter month when the electricity price is high

(IF Question Q6_1 OR Q6_2 OR Q6_3 OR Q6_4 = Yes)

Question Q27: How much money do you need to save on your electricity bill to reduce your electricity consumption with the following measures? Reduce indoor temperature by 3 degrees between kl. 16 and 20 on 1 weekday in the winter while you are at home

(IF Question Q8 = Yes)

Question Q28: How much money do you need to save on your electricity bill to reduce your electricity consumption with the following measures? Do not charge the electric car at home, so you have to stop 1 hour for charging on the next long car trip

Question Q29: Imagine that you buy smart equipment that will reduce your electricity bill by automatically shifting parts of your consumption away from hours with high electricity prices, and you notice nothing. How much do you have to save per year to buy such smart equipment that costs NOK 5,000?

Question Q30: Imagine you could reduce your electricity bill by reducing your electricity consumption during hours of high electricity prices in winter. If you could choose which of the following options would you prefer?

